

Density functional theory in dye chemistry: between the light and the dark side

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Abstract

Some of the most common errors in using density functional theory (DFT) for structural analysis and prediction of the properties of organic azo dyes are considered. The importance on the stabilizing strength of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding, the crucial role of performing conformational analysis and selecting suitable level of theory are discussed using previously published theoretical paper on 2-[2'-(5-nitrothiazolyl)azo]-4-methoxyphenol as a study case. The use of the DFT properties prediction is considered in the frame of the experimental conditions at which they could be measured. It is shown in educational manner why most of the azo dyes do not emit. Although an azo compound is used as example, in general, the same errors and overinterpretations are encountered often when the DFT is applied in the organic chemistry.

Keywords: azo dyes; tautomerism; DFT; optical spectra; conformational analysis

Introduction:

The methods of quantum chemistry, and especially the affordable density functional theory (DFT) methodology, are a powerful tool for prediction of the structural characteristics and spectral properties of organic compounds. Their capacity and practical applicability can be, however, demonstrated in full extent only when the calculations are linked to the experimental reality either as explanation of observed phenomena or as a pre-calibrated predictive tool. Unfortunately, as we stressed several times [1–3], there are cases when the DFT methodology is used just to “calculate” structures and to produce papers, which do not have relation to physical reality and even neglect and distort it. Of course, such “research” could be published only when is “synchronized” with a weak editorial process. We can go even further – the weak editorial process, namely inefficient editorial work, superficial initial quality check of the manuscripts, improper reviewer selection and again lack of quality check of the reviews, is the major reason for appearance of weak scientific content in the corresponding journal.

Currently, in a global view, the problems with quality of the submitted research and with efficiency of the reviewing process is rising. A large number of papers exist, produced within simple concepts like “Conventional synthesis of a single compound - Simple calculations – Undefined promise for potential application” or “Simple calculations of already synthesized by somebody else structures - Predicting properties that are not really needed – Badly speculative promise for potential application”. The computationally affordable DFT is the most common victim of the feeling that everybody can “calculate”, a feeling inspired by the more and more user-friendly computational software. The huge

amount of unneeded calculational results, tables and figures without discussion and without saying something important is a common feature in these cases. Such manuscripts attack the journals like e-mail spam and in many cases, due to the weak reviewing process succeed to get published. As a net result the DFT designed *a-priori* as a useful Swiss knife in organic chemistry becomes a dangerous finger cutting guillotine for people that do not know how to use it.

The reaction of the journal when the harm is detected and shown is critically important. Unfortunately, in many cases a simple reflex “enemy at the gate” is spontaneously activated resulting either in immediate rejection of the criticism with “the Comment is not a manuscript type in our journal” statement or, in a more sophisticated matter, in disproportionately critical and extremely long reviewing process. Actually, the best way to provide a real process of self-healing is to allow comments, replies to them and replies to the replies as long as it is needed until the problem is solved in a healthy scientific discussion. Everybody could benefit from this – the initial authors would get the opportunity to defend their work and if wrong - to learn what is wrong, the readers would get the opportunity to go deeper in the problem facing it from both sides, and the journal would “keep face” and attract attention as an independent platform hosting the discussion.

The chemical community should not turn a blind eye to the problem, because it is not a problem only of the journals. The low quality research has been always existing, but nowadays with the huge number of broad scope scientific journals, the exponentially rising number of submitted papers and the existing very narrow specialization in the individual research, it becomes somehow more anonymous, complicated to be detected and extremely time and efforts consuming to be corrected. We need better to teach and to be more critical, although in the current time of positivism the criticism is often considered as a synonym of hostility. In this context the current note is aimed to consider, from the viewpoint of a non-theoretician, some bad practices (dark side) in the use of DFT calculations in organic chemistry giving practical advices and suggestions what is needed to generate useful, structure supporting theoretical results (to return in the light). As a case study we will use the work “Elucidating the Photophysics and Nonlinear Optical Properties of a Novel Azo Prototype for Possible Photonic Applications: A Quantum Chemical Analysis” by Gester and co-authors [4] following its steps with commentaries what is not properly done and how it could be corrected. The original paper aims to discuss in details the structural properties and optical spectral characteristics of 2-[2'-(5-nitrothiazolyl)azo]-4-methoxyphenol (NTAMP), an o-hydroxy azo dye, previously synthesized and experimentally studied by other authors [5], from the view point of DFT methodology. We will use the same methodology to show that the errors are not a result of the methodology by itself, but come from neglecting the old good laboratory practices of the chemical research.

Theoretical methodology:

Quantum-chemical calculations in the ground and in the first singlet excited state were performed using the Gaussian 16 program suite [6] using respectively DFT and TD-DFT (solving 10 states) methodology for the optimization of the chemical structures. All structures were optimized without restrictions, using tight optimization criteria and an ultrafine grid in the computation of two-electron integrals and their derivatives. The true minima were verified by performing harmonic frequency calculations in the corresponding environment. The implicit solvation was described using the Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM, the integral equation formalism variant, IEFPCM, as implemented in Gaussian 16) [7]. The transition states were estimated using the STQN method [8] and again verified by performing frequency calculations in the corresponding environment.

To provide conditions for comparison wB97XD [9,10], M06-2X [11,12] and CAM-B3LYP [13] density functionals with Pople 6-311++G(d,p) [14,15] basis set were used as in the original paper [4].

For comparison the obtained values for the relative energies in the ground state were validated by using Møller-Plesset MP2-4 [16–19] and CCSD(T) [20,21] single point energies by using 6-311++G(d,p) basis set at wB97XD/6-311++G(d,p) geometry in the corresponding solvent environment.

Results and discussion

1. Importance of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

It is a school teaching example that the o-hydroxy azo dyes exist as conformations, where the intramolecular hydrogen bonding plays a strongly stabilizing role. In a substantial extent their practically important photochemical stability originates from this hydrogen bonding [22,23].

The investigated NTAMP has potentially 16 conformers if the stable trans conformation of the N=N bond is assumed and if the possibility for tautomeric proton exchange (see the discussion below) is not considered. In addition, the traditional planarity of the azo compounds makes the conformational analysis easier. As shown in Figure 1, these conformers are defined by the dihedral angles describing the rotation of the thiazolyl ring (α), the mutual position of the N=N group in respect of the phenolic OH group (β), the mutual position of the OH proton (γ) and the rotation of the OMe group (δ).

The conformational analysis in vacuum and in water, detailed in Tables S1 and S2, respectively, clearly confirms the well-known basic knowledge – the most stable are the structures, where intramolecular hydrogen bonding exists. There are variations, caused by the used functional and the environment (gas phase or water), but they do not change the most stable form shown in Figure 1, right. The structure assumed by Gester and co-authors [4], Figure 1 left, is substantially less stable in both gas phase (8th position in all functionals) and water (9th position at wB97XD and CAM-B3LYP, 10th – at M06-2X). The relative energies in all cases are substantial (over 4 kcal/mol) and beyond the typical error of the DFT calculations. In the paper of Waheeb and co-authors [5], where the experimental data are taken from, most stable form obtained by B3LYP/6-311G(d,p) in vacuum is **III**, a structure where hydrogen bonding also exists, but the thiazolyl ring is in the opposite direction in respect to **I**. To facilitate the discussion below we will denote the corresponding structures as **I** (the most stable one, Figure 1, right) and **VIII** (the structure coming from the paper of Gester and co-workers, Figure 1, left). Whatever is the reason for the selection of **VIII** to be studied, the authors investigate in details a conformer, which does not exist in reality. This makes the overall properties prediction in their paper questionable from the viewpoint of practicability. Bearing in mind that the experimental results are given for dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), the solvent, being strong proton acceptor [24], could potentially break the intramolecular hydrogen bonding and to form intermolecular one, changing γ from 0 to 180°. Even if we assume so, the structure remains quite different from **VIII**.

Here, the first advice comes – do not rush to “calculate” the first structure, which the chemical drawings software gives. It might be wrong. Before to calculate trust to the chemical logic as a first line of defense. In a complex organic molecule, where many degrees of freedom exist, always perform a very detailed conformational analysis. Then predict the properties, because the predicted properties have a practical value only if the structures are really existing.

gas phase

ΔG (wB97XD) = 5.10
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 4.79
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 5.14

ΔG (wB97XD) = 0.0
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 0.0
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 0.0

PCM (water)

ΔG (wB97XD) = 4.41
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 4.31
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 4.58

ΔG (wB97XD) = 0.0
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 0.0
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 0.0

Figure 1. Left: **VIII** - the structure used by Gester and co-authors (Figure 1 in [4]); Right: **I** - the most stable conformer at the same level of theory. Both structures are presented in their azo tautomeric form. The relative Gibbs energies in kcal/mol units are listed for comparison (see Tables S1 and S2). The dihedral angles are defined as follows: α – N1-N2-C8-N3; β – C6-C5-N1-N2; γ – C5-C6-O1-H3 and δ – C4-C3-O2-C7.

2. DFT reality, which does not correspond to the experimental knowledge.

DFT is the most widely accepted model for calculating the electronic structure of organic compounds, but its applications rely on approximations to the unknown exact exchange–correlation functional [25–28]. The existing nowadays “zoo” of functionals has been created by fitting against existing experimental or high-level theoretical data. In this way no one of these functionals is universal and

a-priori suitable outside the data used for its creation. There is a substantial possibility that the artificial theoretical reality, created by a given functional, could not correspond to the experimental reality which it aims to describe. Usually, the evil is in details and the best way is to check the adequacy of the created model against existing experimental data before to make definite conclusions.

It is well known that o-hydroxy azo dyes exhibit azo-quinonehydrazone tautomerism, which is structurally determined by the presence of the OH group on a suitable position (Figure 2). In this respect, the resonance stabilization energy (i.e. reduced aromaticity of the OH containing ring) plays the decisive role going from azo to quinonehydrazone tautomer, which is the reason why the azophenols exist as single azo tautomers as a rule [22,23]. NTAMP falls exactly in this category. According to the existing experimental data [5], there is no sights of tautomeric equilibrium in NTAMP and it can be considered as an exclusive azo tautomer. This gives a good opportunity to check the reliability of the density functionals, i.e. the theoretical reality, used in [4]. It has been known previously that wB97XD and CAM-B3LYP are not suitable for describing tautomeric azo dyes [29,30], because strongly overestimate the stability of the quinonehydrazone form. This can be very easily checked here as well. By using wB97XD, the quinonehydrazone tautomer of **I** (**IH**, Figure 2) seems to be almost equally stable in water to the azo form – its relative Gibbs energy changes from 1.4 to 0.07 kcal/mol (from gas phase to water respectively). The situation with CAM-B3LYP is very similar – the relative Gibbs energy of the quinonehydrazone is 1.3 kcal/mol in gas phase and it is even predicted to be slightly more stable compared to the azo form (by 0.01 kcal/mol) in water. In other words, the use of wB97XD and CAM-B3LYP creates a theoretical reality, which strongly disagrees with the experimental facts. In this reality the non-existing quinonehydrazone tautomer **IH** seems to be available in measurable amounts and, even worse, to be more probable compared even with the wrongly assumed conformer **VIII**, discussed in the previous section. The use of M06-2X, which is, based on our experience, one of the best functionals for prediction of tautomeric state in organic compounds, leads to relative Gibbs energy of 3.7 and 2.6 kcal/mol (gas phase and water, respectively), which corresponds to the experimental knowledge of azophenols existing as only azo tautomers. A detailed comparison between the stabilities of the tautomers in DMSO, where the compound is soluble [5], predicted by the used density functionals and post-Hartree-Fock methods can be made considering the data in Table 1. As seen, the much more precise and reliable MPn and CCSD methods clearly predict the much stronger stability of the azo tautomer and, hence, suitability of using M06-2X functional.

Azo (IA)

ΔG (wB97XD) = 0.0
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 0.0
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 0.0

ΔG (wB97XD) = 0.0
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 0.0
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 0.01

Quinonehydrazone (IH)
 gas phase

ΔG (wB97XD) = 1.38
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 3.69
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 1.31

PCM (water)

ΔG (wB97XD) = 0.07
 ΔG (M06-2X) = 2.60
 ΔG (CAM-B3LYP) = 0.0

Figure 2. Possible tautomers of NTAMP arising from the most stable conformer I. The listed relative Gibbs energies are in kcal/mol units.

Table 1. Predicted relative stabilities (in kcal/mol units) of the tautomers of I in DMSO.

Theory	IA		IH	
	ΔE	ΔG	ΔE	ΔG
CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)	0.0	0.0	0.18	0.01
M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p)	0.0	0.0	2.64	2.61
wB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)	0.0	0.0	0.32	0.08
MP2/6-311++G(d,p)//	0.0	-	6.55	-

wB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)				
MP3/6-311++G(d,p)// wB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)	0.0	-	3.58	-
MP4/6-311++G(d,p)// wB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)	0.0	-	3.20	-
CCSD/6-311++G(d,p)// wB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)	0.0	-	2.18	-
CCSD(T)/6-311++G(d,p)// wB97XD/6-311++G(d,p)	0.0	-	3.20	-

This comes to indicate the importance of selecting suitable level of theory and the fact that this selection must be validated by the experimentally existing data and knowledge. The theoretical reality is always correct from computational point of view, but, more important is to create a reality which correctly describes the experiment.

3. Selection of the environmental conditions for the calculations.

Much efforts are taken to predict and discuss the spectral properties of NTAMP in vacuum (gas phase) and in water [4]. I have never seen optical spectra of an azo dye, measured in a gas phase. The spectra in gas phase can be measured only if the compound is volatile enough at given conditions, which is not the case in most of the azo compounds (including NTAMP) in the normally accessible experimental conditions. As clearly stated previously [5], the compound is not soluble in water, but in DMSO. In such a case the very detailed discussion about the possible spectral and structural changes going from gas phase, where they cannot be measured, to water, where the compound is not soluble, does not make sense and should be considered just as unneeded calculational exercise.

It is mentioned that the observed absorption results from S_0 - S_2 vertical transition (π - π^*) [4]. The n - π^* (S_0 - S_1) transition being symmetry forbidden ends to a dark state in most of the azo dyes, a well-known fact [31], and in NTAMP in particular according to the common tendency. Concerning this fact and the lack of experimentally detected emission [5], the prediction of the emission properties is not practically meaningful.

Azo dyes do not emit or emission in *o*-hydroxy azo dyes is extremely weak [32]. Below, educationally, we explain why no emission is possible for NTAMP. The model is based on M06-2X, which is, as shown above, appropriate to describe properties of *o*-hydroxy azo dyes.

The *o*-hydroxy azo dyes contain two fragments, each of which bring different and contradicting photophysical properties. Azo group is a source of *cis/trans* isomerization, while the *o*-OH group potentially can lead to excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT [33]) upon excitation. In Figure 3 only these competitive processes are sketched for simplicity.

Figure 3. Simplified sketch of the possible processes in the ground and first singlet excited (both M06-2X/6-311+G(d,p)) state of **I** in DMSO. The stable structures are indicated in blue, the transition states are given in red, constrained structures are colored in brown. The S_2 Frank-Condon state of **IA** is shown in green. The relative energies and relative Gibbs energies, separated by a slash, are given in kcal/mol units. The oscillator strengths of the excited states are listed in square brackets. The values of β and the twisting angle C5-N1-N2-C8, related to the cis/trans isomerization around the N=N bond, are given in parentheses.

Figure 3 shows a typical ground state behavior of an azophenol. The planar trans azo form is substantially more stable in the ground state, while the corresponding **H**-form and the cis **A**-form are with energies that could not suggest an equilibrium mixture. Consequently, as already discussed above, the excitation yields S_2 Frank-Condon state and as there are no experimental evidences and structural conditions (such as non-benzenoid aromatic hydrocarbons or heterocyclic organic molecules) to expect anti-Kasha emission behavior [34–41], it, through internal conversion, relaxes to the azo S_1 state. The optimization in the S_1 state leads to a twisting around the N=N bond and we were not able to get stable structure without constrains. The constrained planar structure has an imaginary frequency and the attempt for relaxed scan of the twisting around N=N bond was only partially successful (ends at

-130°), leading to decrease of the energy (brown colored data in the Figure). Then the process becomes unstable, which is not surprising because the conventional TD-DFT is not suitable for calculations in the conical intersection region [42–47]. However, all this information is in agreement with experimental data and the existing high level calculations of the excited state behavior of azo compounds, which prove that the excited to ground state relaxation proceeds through conical intersection, where the planarity of the compound is substantially disturbed [48–53]. This explains why no emission could be observed from the azo tautomer. The only emission could come from the excited **H**-form, but in this particular case, as seen from the Figure, the probability is extremely low. The ESIPT generated emission is very weak, practically comparable with the level of the instrumental noise [32], even in the o-hydroxy azonaphthols, where the **H**-tautomers are experimentally observed. Therefore, the prediction of the emission properties of NTAMP does not have practical value.

The theoretical prediction of properties has to be always done at condition, which correspond to a practical possibility to be measured. There is no practical reason to predict properties for which is known that do not exist or are negligibly small to be experimentally measured.

Conclusions:

Based on the discussion above, we give some good laboratory practice advices how to stay in the light for the researchers who use DFT in structure elucidation and properties predictions in organic chemistry and in dye chemistry in particular: always perform conformational analysis of molecules where rotational degrees of freedom are available, always predict properties at conditions allowing to be experimentally confirmed or compared, always predict properties that really exist. Even if from calculational point of view everything looks correctly it might be wrong from experimental point of view when an inappropriate density functional is chosen. The most obvious conclusion is that a critical view on the produced calculational results and understanding of the existing experimental facts is needed to provide a realistic, practically useful and valuable theoretical description of a given compound or process.

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Supporting Information: Table S1. Conformers of NTAMP, ranked by rise of the Gibbs energy in gas phase. Table S2. Conformers of NTAMP, ranked by rise of the Gibbs energy in water.

References:

- [1] Nedeltcheva-Antonova D, Antonov L. Comment on “Influence of Solvents and Halogenation on ESIPT of Benzimidazole Derivatives for Designing Turn-on Fluorescence Probes.” *ACS Omega* 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.5c01348>. 259-262
- [2] Antonov L, Lyčka A. A correction of the neglected tautomerism in the spectra prediction of o-methoxyaniline terminated monoazonaphthols: DFT and ¹⁵N NMR study. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 2024;406:125134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2024.125134>. 263-265
- [3] Antonov L, Hansen PE, Zwan G van der. Comment on “Spectroscopic studies of keto–enol tautomeric equilibrium of azo dyes” by M. A. Rauf, S. Hisaindee and N. Saleh, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 18097. *RSC Advances* 2015;5:67165–7. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RA10553F>. 266-268
- [4] Fonseca S, Dos Santos NSS, Georg HC, Fonseca TL, Provasi PF, Coutinho K, et al. Elucidating the Photo-physics and Nonlinear Optical Properties of a Novel Azo Prototype for Possible Photonic Applications: A Quantum Chemical Analysis. *ACS Omega* 2024;9:40583–91. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c04240>. 269-272
- [5] Waheeb AS, Kadhim Kyhoiesh HA, Salman AW, Al-Adilee KJ, Kadhim MM. Metal complexes of a new azo ligand 2-[2'-(5-nitrothiazolyl) azo]-4-methoxyphenol (NTAMP): Synthesis, spectral characterization, and theoretical calculation. *Inorganic Chemistry Communications* 2022;138:109267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2022.109267>. 273-276
- [6] Frisch MJ, Trucks GW, Schlegel HB, Scuseria GE, Robb MA, Cheeseman JR, et al. *Gaussian 16 Rev. C.01* 2016. 277-278
- [7] Tomasi J, Mennucci B, Cammi R. Quantum Mechanical Continuum Solvation Models. *Chemical Reviews* 2005;105:2999–3094. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr9904009>. 279-280
- [8] Peng C, Ayala PY, Schlegel HB, Frisch MJ. Using redundant internal coordinates to optimize equilibrium geometries and transition states. *Journal of Computational Chemistry* 1996;17:49–56. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-987X\(19960115\)17:1%3C49::AID-JCC5%3E3.0.CO;2-0](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-987X(19960115)17:1%3C49::AID-JCC5%3E3.0.CO;2-0). 281-283
- [9] Chai J-D, Head-Gordon M. Systematic optimization of long-range corrected hybrid density functionals. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 2008;128:084106. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2834918>. 284-285
- [10] Chai J-D, Head-Gordon M. Long-range corrected hybrid density functionals with damped atom–atom dispersion corrections. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* 2008;10:6615. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b810189b>. 286-288
- [11] Zhao Y, Truhlar DG. Density Functionals with Broad Applicability in Chemistry. *Accounts of Chemical Research* 2008;41:157–67. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar700111a>. 289-290
- [12] Zhao Y, Truhlar DG. The M06 suite of density functionals for main group thermochemistry, thermochemical kinetics, noncovalent interactions, excited states, and transition elements: two new functionals and systematic testing of four M06-class functionals and 12 other functionals. *Theoretical Chemistry Accounts* 2008;120:215–41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00214-007-0310-x>. 291-294
- [13] Yanai T, Tew DP, Handy NC. A new hybrid exchange–correlation functional using the Coulomb-attenuating method (CAM-B3LYP). *Chemical Physics Letters* 2004;393:51–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2004.06.011>. 295-297
- [14] Clark T, Chandrasekhar J, Spitznagel GW, Schleyer PVR. Efficient diffuse function-augmented basis sets for anion calculations. III. The 3-21+G basis set for first-row elements, Li–F. *J Comput Chem* 1983;4:294–301. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcc.540040303>. 298-300

- [15] Krishnan R, Binkley JS, Seeger R, Pople JA. Self-consistent molecular orbital methods. XX. A basis set for correlated wave functions. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 1980;72:650–4. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.438955>. 301
302
303
- [16] Head-Gordon M, Head-Gordon T. Analytic MP2 frequencies without fifth-order storage. Theory and application to bifurcated hydrogen bonds in the water hexamer. *Chemical Physics Letters* 1994;220:122–8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614\(94\)00116-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614(94)00116-2). 304
305
306
- [17] Frisch MJ, Head-Gordon M, Pople JA. A direct MP2 gradient method. *Chemical Physics Letters* 1990;166:275–80. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614\(90\)80029-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614(90)80029-D). 307
308
- [18] Pople JA, Seeger R, Krishnan R. Variational configuration interaction methods and comparison with perturbation theory. *Int J Quantum Chem* 2009;12:149–63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qua.560120820>. 309
310
- [19] Krishnan R, Frisch MJ, Pople JA. Contribution of triple substitutions to the electron correlation energy in fourth order perturbation theory. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 1980;72:4244–5. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.439657>. 311
312
313
- [20] Purvis GD, Bartlett RJ. A full coupled-cluster singles and doubles model: The inclusion of disconnected triples. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 1982;76:1910–8. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.443164>. 314
315
- [21] Pople JA, Head-Gordon M, Raghavachari K. Quadratic configuration interaction. A general technique for determining electron correlation energies. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 1987;87:5968–75. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.453520>. 316
317
318
- [22] Gordon PF, Gregory P. *Azo Dyes*. Organic Chemistry in Colour, Berlin: Springer-Verlag; 1987. 319
- [23] Zollinger H. *Color chemistry: syntheses, properties, and applications of organic dyes and pigments*. 3rd, rev. ed ed. Zürich : Weinheim: Verlag Helvetica Chimica Acta ; Wiley-VCH; 2003. 320
321
- [24] Reichardt C, Welton T. *Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry*. Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA; 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527632220>. 322
323
- [25] Brémond E, Pérez-Jiménez AJ, Adamo C, Sancho-García JC. Contemporary DFT: learning from traditional and recent trends for the development and assessment of accurate exchange–correlation functionals. *Phys Chem Chem Phys* 2026;28:3779–96. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D5CP03373J>. 324
325
326
- [26] Bursch M, Mewes J, Hansen A, Grimme S. Best-Practice DFT Protocols for Basic Molecular Computational Chemistry**. *Angew Chem Int Ed* 2022;61:e202205735. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202205735>. 327
328
329
- [27] Geerlings P, De Proft F, Langenaeker W. Conceptual Density Functional Theory. *Chem Rev* 2003;103:1793–874. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr990029p>. 330
331
- [28] Morgante P, Peverati R. The devil in the details: A tutorial review on some undervalued aspects of density functional theory calculations. *Int J of Quantum Chemistry* 2020;120:e26332. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qua.26332>. 332
333
334
- [29] Kawachi S, Antonov L. Description of the Tautomerism in Some Azonaphthols. *Journal of Physical Organic Chemistry* 2013;26:643–52. <https://doi.org/10.1002/poc.3143>. 335
336
- [30] Antonov L. Tautomerism in Azo and Azomethyne Dyes: When and If Theory Meets Experiment. *Molecules* 2019;24:2252. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24122252>. 337
338
- [31] Fabian J, Hartmann H. *Light absorption of organic colorants: theoretical treatment and empirical rules*. Berlin: Springer-Verlag; 1980. 339
340
- [32] Joshi H, Kamounah FS, Gooijer C, van der Zwan G, Antonov L. Excited state intramolecular proton transfer in some tautomeric azo dyes and schiff bases containing an intramolecular hydrogen bond. *Journal* 341
342

- of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry 2002;152:183–91. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1010-6030\(02\)00155-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1010-6030(02)00155-7). 343
- [33] Joshi HC, Antonov L. Excited-State Intramolecular Proton Transfer: A Short Introductory Review. *Molecules* 2021;26:1475. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26051475>. 344
- [34] Tseng H-W, Shen J-Y, Kuo T-Y, Tu T-S, Chen Y-A, Demchenko AP, et al. Excited-state intramolecular proton-transfer reaction demonstrating anti-Kasha behavior. *Chem Sci* 2016;7:655–65. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5SC01945A>. 345
- [35] Shi L, Yan C, Guo Z, Chi W, Wei J, Liu W, et al. De novo strategy with engineering anti-Kasha/Kasha fluorophores enables reliable ratiometric quantification of biomolecules. *Nat Commun* 2020;11:793. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-14615-3>. 346
- [36] Shekhovtsov NA, Nikolaenkova EB, Berezin AS, Plyusnin VF, Vinogradova KA, Naumov DYU, et al. A 1-Hydroxy-1 H -imidazole ESIPT Emitter Demonstrating anti-Kasha Fluorescence and Direct Excitation of a Tautomeric Form. *ChemPlusChem* 2021;86:1436–41. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cplu.202100370>. 347
- [37] Shekhovtsov NA, Bushuev MB. Anomalous emission of an ESIPT-capable zinc(II) complex: An interplay of TADF, TICT and anti-Kasha behaviour. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry* 2022;433:114195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotochem.2022.114195>. 348
- [38] Zhang X, Chen C, Zhang W, Yin N, Yuan B, Zhuang G, et al. Anomalous anti-Kasha excited-state luminescence from symmetry-breaking heterogeneous carbon bisnanohoops. *Nat Commun* 2024;15:2684. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-46848-x>. 349
- [39] Shekhovtsov NA, Bushuev MB. Excited state dynamics of azulene and its derivatives: The impact of energy gap and vibronic coupling on anti-Kasha emission in solution. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 2025;425:127260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2025.127260>. 350
- [40] Yang X, Yang D, Li B. Electrochemical Annulation of Phenothiazines with Alkynes: Access to Anti-Kasha Triple-Emission, Light-Sensitive, and Room-Temperature Phosphorescent Materials. *J Am Chem Soc* 2025;147:30390–400. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.5c09956>. 351
- [41] Shekhovtsov N, Bushuev MB. Non-adiabatic quantum dynamics of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons exhibiting anti-Kasha emission from the S₂ state. *Phys Chem Chem Phys* 2026;10.1039.D5CP03865K. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D5CP03865K>. 352
- [42] Matsika S. Electronic Structure Methods for the Description of Nonadiabatic Effects and Conical Intersections. *Chem Rev* 2021;121:9407–49. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.1c00074>. 353
- [43] Park W, Komarov K, Lee S, Choi CH. Mixed-Reference Spin-Flip Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory: Multireference Advantages with the Practicality of Linear Response Theory. *J Phys Chem Lett* 2023;14:8896–908. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.3c02296>. 354
- [44] Lee S, Park W, Choi CH. Expanding Horizons in Quantum Chemical Studies: The Versatile Power of MRSF-TDDFT. *Acc Chem Res* 2025;58:208–17. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.accounts.4c00640>. 355
- [45] Teh H-H, Subotnik JE. The Simplest Possible Approach for Simulating S₀ – S₁ Conical Intersections with DFT/TDDFT: Adding *One* Doubly Excited Configuration. *J Phys Chem Lett* 2019;10:3426–32. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.9b00981>. 356
- [46] Zhang X, Wang T, Gao YQ, Xiao Y. Noncollinear Spin-Flip TDDFT for Potential Energy Surface Crossings: Conical Intersections and Spin Crossings. *J Chem Theory Comput* 2025;21:11550–61. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.5c01272>. 357
- [47] Huix-Rotllant M, Nikiforov A, Thiel W, Filatov M. Description of Conical Intersections with Density Functional Methods. In: Ferré N, Filatov M, Huix-Rotllant M, editors. *Density-Functional Methods for Excited* 358

- States, vol. 368, Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2015, p. 445–76. https://doi.org/10.1007/128_2015_631. 386
387
- [48] Tamai N, Miyasaka H. Ultrafast Dynamics of Photochromic Systems. *Chem Rev* 2000;100:1875–90. 388
<https://doi.org/10.1021/cr9800816>. 389
- [49] Casellas J, Bearpark MJ, Reguero M. Excited-State Decay in the Photoisomerisation of Azobenzene: A 390
New Balance between Mechanisms. *ChemPhysChem* 2016;17:3068–79. 391
<https://doi.org/10.1002/cphc.201600502>. 392
- [50] Schnack-Petersen AK, Pápai M, Møller KB. Azobenzene photoisomerization dynamics: Revealing the key 393
degrees of freedom and the long timescale of the trans-to-cis process. *Journal of Photochemistry and* 394
Photobiology A: Chemistry 2022;428:113869. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotochem.2022.113869>. 395
- [51] Satzger H, Root C, Braun M. Excited-State Dynamics of *trans* - and *cis* -Azobenzene after UV Excitation 396
in the $\pi\pi^*$ Band. *J Phys Chem A* 2004;108:6265–71. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp049509x>. 397
- [52] Tan EMM, Amirjalayer S, Smolarek S, Vdovin A, Zerbetto F, Buma WJ. Fast photodynamics of azoben- 398
zene probed by scanning excited-state potential energy surfaces using slow spectroscopy. *Nat Commun* 399
2015;6:5860. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6860>. 400
- [53] Merritt ICD, Jacquemin D, Vacher M. *cis* \rightarrow *trans* photoisomerisation of azobenzene: a fresh theoretical 401
look. *Phys Chem Chem Phys* 2021;23:19155–65. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1CP01873F>. 402
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Supporting Information

Density functional theory in dye chemistry: between the light and the dark side

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Table S1. Conformers of NTAMP, ranked by rise of the Gibbs energy in gas phase. The conformer considered in the original paper is shadowed.

	dihedral angles (Figure 1)				μ [D]	ΔE	$\Delta E+ZPE$	ΔG
	α [°]	β [°]	γ [°]	δ [°]		[kcal/mol]		
ω B97XD								
I	180	0	0	0	5.2	0.00	0.00	0.00
II	180	0	0	180	6.7	1.36	1.29	1.15
III	0	0	0	0	5.4	4.14	4.03	1.75
IV	180	180	0	0	5.3	2.61	2.57	2.20
V	180	180	0	180	6.7	4.43	4.11	3.49
VI	0	180	0	0	4.9	4.53	4.47	3.78
VII	-10	-1	0	180	6.7	5.59	5.39	4.58
VIII	0	180	0	180	6.5	6.20	5.96	5.10
IX	180	180	180	0	7.2	7.94	7.26	6.39
X	180	180	180	180	9.1	9.56	8.77	7.41
XI	180	0	180	0	7.2	11.25	10.69	9.84
XII	180	0	180	180	9.3	12.15	11.51	10.53
XIII	-20	176	178	0	7.0	12.31	11.72	10.69
XIV	21	-174	-178	180	9.0	13.72	13.00	11.89
XV	17	3	178	0	7.0	14.39	13.76	12.65
XVI	-20	-7	-177	180	9.0	15.40	14.69	13.41
M06-2X*								
I	180	0	0	0	4.9	0.00	0.00	0.00
II	180	0	0	180	6.6	1.28	1.23	1.10
IV	180	180	0	0	5.2	1.88	1.84	1.49
V	180	180	0	180	6.6	3.68	3.50	3.02
VI	0	180	0	0	4.7	3.94	3.97	3.43

III	0	0	0	0	5.2	4.26	4.17	3.44
VII	-5	0	0	180	6.5	5.65	5.50	4.52
VIII	0	180	0	180	6.3	5.58	5.46	4.79
IX	180	180	180	0	7.1	6.94	6.35	5.32
X	180	180	180	180	9.0	8.53	7.82	6.45
XI	180	0	180	0	7.0	10.32	9.83	8.91
XII	180	0	180	180	9.2	11.15	10.55	9.31
XIII	-9	179	179	0	6.9	11.53	10.89	9.92
XIV	0	180	180	180	8.9	12.90	12.08	9.95
XV	0	0	180	0	6.8	13.51	12.89	10.85
XVI	-9	-6	-177	180	8.8	14.48	13.83	12.17
CAM-B3LYP*								
I	180	0	0	0	5.2	0.00	0.00	0.00
II	180	0	0	180	6.8	1.38	1.28	1.11
III	0	0	0	0	5.6	4.09	3.94	2.25
IV	180	180	0	0	5.4	2.93	2.79	2.37
V	180	180	0	180	6.8	4.76	4.44	3.81
VI	0	180	0	0	4.9	4.65	4.54	3.84
VII	-6	0	0	180	6.8	5.58	5.37	4.30
VIII	0	180	0	180	6.6	6.30	6.04	5.14
IX	180	180	180	0	7.2	8.22	7.55	6.68
X	180	180	180	180	9.2	9.83	9.01	7.69
XI	180	0	180	0	7.2	11.53	10.92	10.00
XII	180	0	180	180	9.4	12.41	11.67	10.50
XIII	-17	177	178	0	7.1	12.53	11.84	10.81
XIV	-18	176	178	180	9.1	13.95	13.14	11.89
XV	-15	-4	-178	0	7.1	14.52	13.84	12.64
XVI	-18	-7	-177	180	9.1	15.53	14.77	13.51

* The annotations of the conformers from ω B97XD is used.

Table S2. Conformers of NTAMP, ranked by rise of the Gibbs energy in water. The conformer considered in the original paper is shadowed.

	dihedral angles (Figure 1)				μ [D]	ΔE	$\Delta E+ZPE$	ΔG
	α [°]	β [°]	γ [°]	δ [°]		[kcal/mol]		
ω B97XD*								
I	180	0	0	0	6.2	0.00	0.00	0.00
II	180	0	0	180	8.4	1.05	0.96	0.84
IV	180	180	0	0	6.3	1.72	1.65	1.45
V	180	180	0	180	8.4	3.00	2.75	2.40
III	0	0	0	0	6.2	3.10	3.03	2.72
VI	0	180	0	0	5.7	4.49	4.28	3.39
VII	0	0	0	180	8.1	4.10	3.91	3.44
IX	180	180	180	0	9.1	4.68	4.33	3.87
VIII	0	180	0	180	8.0	5.76	5.43	4.41
X	180	180	180	180	11.7	5.79	5.37	4.78
XIII	0	180	180	0	8.6	8.05	7.52	6.25
XI	180	0	180	0	9.1	7.31	7.02	6.38
XII	180	0	180	180	12.0	7.93	7.60	6.91
XIV	0	180	180	180	11.4	9.10	8.55	7.36
XV	21	7	178	0	8.7	10.74	10.36	9.50
XVI	-21	-7	-177	180	11.4	11.30	10.85	9.71
M06-2X*								
I	180	0	0	0	5.8	0.00	0.00	0.00
II	180	0	0	180	8.1	0.97	0.94	0.86
IV	180	180	0	0	6.0	1.00	1.02	0.90
V	180	180	0	180	8.1	2.25	2.20	2.03
III	0	0	0	0	5.8	3.18	3.14	2.95

VI	0	180	0	0	5.4	3.83	3.77	3.15
IX	180	180	180	0	8.8	3.77	3.54	3.16
VII	0	0	0	180	7.7	4.12	4.03	3.60
X	180	180	180	180	11.5	4.84	4.52	4.05
VIII	0	180	0	180	7.7	5.07	4.94	4.31
XI	180	0	180	0	8.8	6.47	6.24	5.56
XIII	0	180	180	0	8.4	7.18	6.78	5.90
XII	180	0	180	180	11.7	7.03	6.73	5.97
XIV	0	180	180	180	11.2	8.18	7.74	6.87
XV	0	0	180	0	8.4	9.93	9.64	8.78
XVI	-8	-5	-178	180	11.2	10.46	10.18	9.22
CAM-B3LYP*								
I	180	0	0	0	6.4	0.00	0.00	0.00
II	180	0	0	180	8.6	1.05	0.98	0.83
IV	180	180	0	0	6.4	2.06	1.96	1.75
III	0	0	0	0	6.4	3.05	2.95	2.67
V	180	180	0	180	8.5	3.32	3.13	2.81
VII	0	0	0	180	8.2	4.07	3.93	3.45
VI	0	180	0	0	5.8	4.65	4.45	3.62
IX	180	180	180	0	9.3	5.03	4.68	4.26
VIII	0	180	0	180	8.1	5.89	5.59	4.58
X	180	180	180	180	11.9	6.11	5.66	5.08
XI	180	0	180	0	9.2	7.65	7.31	6.61
XIII	-9	179	180	0	8.8	8.29	7.79	6.93
XII	180	0	180	180	12.1	8.24	7.82	7.01
XIV	-9	179	180	180	11.6	9.30	8.73	7.65
XV	-17	-5	-178	0	8.8	10.99	10.57	9.37
XVI	-18	-7	-178	180	11.6	11.52	11.08	10.12

* The annotations of the conformers from ω B97XD in gas phase is used.